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Contact X-ray Brachytherapy (CXB) as a boost therapy after neoadjuvant (chemo)radiation in high-risk locally advanced rectal cancer

Short running title: Contact radiation in high-risk rectal cancer

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Data availability statement

Research data are stored in the institutional repository and anonymised data will be shared upon request to the corresponding author.

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Abstract

Background and purpose

Radical surgery following neoadjuvant therapy is the standard of care for locally advanced rectal cancer. A Contact X-ray Brachytherapy (CXB) boost can alternatively be used to treat residual disease post neoadjuvant (chemo)radiation, especially in patients who are not suitable for or do not wish to have surgery. Its role has mostly been studied to date in low to intermediate-risk patients. We have now evaluated the utility of CXB-boost in high-risk rectal cancers after their tumours have been significantly downstaged by neoadjuvant (chemo)radiation.

Materials and methods

Oncological outcomes and treatment tolerability were evaluated in 328 patients based on rectal cancer treatment risk stratification: low/intermediate risk (cT1-3ab, N0-1, M0, no extramural invasion (EMVI), mesorectal fascia (MRF) involvement >1mm) and high-risk (cT3cd-4/N2, M0, MRF≤1mm and/or EMVI positive).

Results

With median follow-up of 33 (IQR:15-54) months and median age of 73 (IQR:62-80) years, no significant differences were found between low/intermediate and high-risk groups in clinical complete response (78% vs 73%, $p=0.32$), local regrowth (16.6% vs 22.4%, $p=0.41$), nodal (1.8% vs 5.8%, $p=0.051$) or regional (1.3% vs 2.9%, $p=0.33$) relapse, or post-radiation toxicities ($p=0.16$). However, the high-risk group had a higher distant relapse rate (21.2% vs 10.7%, $p=0.01$), with no significant differences in 3-year organ preservation (80% vs 87%, $p=0.25$), 5-year disease-free (DFS) (62% vs 64%, $p=0.46$), or overall (OS) survivals (67% vs 64%, $p=0.88$). Longer treatment time, treatment gap >24 weeks between therapies, and administration of a higher than standard CXB dose were newly identified factors that negatively impacted outcomes.

Conclusions

High-risk rectal cancer patients treated with CXB-boost had more distant relapses, but comparable locoregional tumour control, organ preservation, DFS and OS to lower-risk patients, with acceptable toxicities. CXB-boost is therefore a viable option for selected high-risk rectal cancer patients. Timely reassessment, prompt referral, and CXB dose optimisation are crucial for improving outcomes.

Short running title: Contact radiotherapy in high-risk rectal cancer

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Introduction

Current guidelines for managing locally advanced rectal cancer recommend starting with neoadjuvant treatment, including total neoadjuvant therapy, (chemo)radiation, or immunotherapy based on tumour stage and molecular mismatch repair (MMR) status, followed by radical total mesorectal excision (TME) [1-3]. This multi-modality approach reduces pelvic recurrence (2.4-15%) and improves 5-year overall survival (64-87%) [4-6]. However, these benefits come at the cost of post-operative complications [7], stoma formation, and functional impairment of pelvic organs [8, 9].

Over the past two decades, organ-preserving strategies, including local excisions and radiation dose-escalation treatments after neoadjuvant therapy, have been adopted to avoid complications related to general anaesthesia and surgery [10], and to respect patients' preferences to avoid extirpative surgery [11]. Published evidence reports that non-surgical treatment achieves long-term organ preservation (59-97%), disease-free survival (61-94%), and overall survival (71-91%) [12-16].

The UK National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) currently recommends the use of contact X-ray brachytherapy (CXB) only for high surgical risk patients who have early-stage rectal cancer, emphasising its safety and efficacy for these cases. However it is not currently recommended for locally advanced tumours, unless in a research context [17, 18]. However, in routine clinical practice, CXB is used for various indications with informed patient consent, due to the higher bowel cancer incidence in the elderly [19], increased comorbidities with advancing age [20], and patients' preferences to avoid colostomy [11]. CXB can be used alone or as adjuvant therapy after local excision in stage-I rectal cancer, as a boost combined with (chemo)radiation in operable/more advanced tumours, and also as an alternative salvage option for luminal regrowth after watch-and-wait surveillance [21-24].

Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) is the standard for initial and post-therapy (re)staging and determining treatment risk categories to guide neoadjuvant therapy in rectal cancer management [25]. Over recent years, the definition of high-risk features in locally advanced rectal cancer has

evolved [26], with low-risk tumours currently being defined as cT1-3abN0M0, tumour to mesorectal rectal fascia (MRF) distance >1mm and no extramural venous invasion(EMVI); intermediate-risk as cT1-3abN1-2M0, MRF >1mm, no EMVI; and high-risk as cT3cd-4anyNM0, anycTN2M0, MRF ≤1mm, and/or presence of EMVI [2, 3].

Numerous studies, including two randomised controlled trials, have investigated the efficacy of CXB as a boost therapy for residual disease following neoadjuvant (chemo)radiation, but these have primarily focused on low and intermediate-risk rectal cancers [23, 27-31]. The ongoing OPAXX phase II study is currently recruiting patients to assess the one-year organ preservation rate after a CXB boost for good responders (small residual/near Complete Response (nCR)) after neoadjuvant treatment in intermediate/high-risk patients [32]. However, comprehensive reports about the efficacy of CXB boost in combination with (chemo)radiation in this context are currently lacking.

We therefore conducted this study to investigate the oncological outcomes of CXB-boost therapy after significant downstaging with neoadjuvant (chemo)radiation in high-risk versus low/intermediate-risk rectal cancer patients using MRI-based treatment risk stratification along with the impact of patient-related factors, tumour characteristics, and treatment on oncological outcomes and tolerability.

Materials and methods

Patient selection

Institutional audit approval was obtained on 3rd May 2022 for a retrospective review of all sequential patients who had undergone both (chemo)radiation and CXB with curative intent at our centre from 2008 to 2019. Patient demographics, tumour characteristics, detailed MRI staging reports, treatment details, and outcome data were entered into an institutional CXB database system and subsequently analysed.

Neoadjuvant treatment

Neoadjuvant external beam radiation (EBRT) was administered in one of three regimens: chemoradiation (45-54Gy/25-30 fractions/5-6 weeks), or long-course (40-50Gy/20-25 fractions/4-5 weeks), or short-course (25Gy/5 fractions/1 week) radiotherapy alone, chosen based on patient performance status and comorbidities. Initially, conformal 3-dimensional radiation (3D-CRT) was the primary technique used, with a transition to Intensity Modulated Radiation Therapy (IMRT) after 2013. (Neo)adjuvant chemotherapy was not routinely administered before or following radiotherapy. Patients were reassessed using digital rectal examination (DRE), sigmoidoscopy, and/or restaging MRI scans. Those who had significant downstaging (small residual disease/near clinical Complete Response (nCR)) after neoadjuvant therapy were referred for consideration of CXB. (*Supplementary figure 1*)

Contact X-ray Brachytherapy (CXB) as a boost therapy

Patients referred from local colorectal cancer multidisciplinary teams (MDTs) across the United Kingdom were reviewed before starting CXB at the CXB MDT meeting. Suitability for administration of CXB with curative intent was assessed by digital rectal examination (DRE), identifying small, mobile or slightly tethered residual disease (≤ 3 cm) located within 10 cm of the anal verge. Additionally, post-neoadjuvant sigmoidoscopy and/or MRI findings had to show significant tumour downstaging and downsizing compared to pre-treatment imaging, with no evidence of nodal involvement. Treatment intent were discussed and patients were informed that CXB is not the standard care in our country and that surgery may have to be reconsidered if residual tumour or regrowth occurred following treatment. All patients were requested to sign a consent form before treatment initiation. CXB was delivered on an outpatient basis using the Papillon-50[®] machine (50kVp X-rays, HVL 0.64 mm Al, 2.7 mA; Ariane, Alfreton, UK). The radiation dose of 20-30Gy was administered at each fraction two weeks apart via a rectal treatment applicator (sizes 30, 25, or 22 mm) at focal source-surface distances of 29, 32, or 38 mm, respectively. A standard dose of 90Gy (rectal mucosa surface dose) was delivered in 3 fractions over 4 weeks. A fourth 20Gy dose (total

110Gy) was administered to selected patients who had minimal visible and/ palpable tumours still present after the third fraction.

Follow-up

Patients achieving complete or near-clinical responses (cCR/nCR) at 8-12 weeks post-treatment were regularly monitored. Follow-up included DRE, flexible sigmoidoscopy/rigid rectoscopy alternately at the patient's local colorectal centre and our centre (if the patients were prepared to attend regular appointments at our centre), with MRI scans every 12 weeks for the first 2 years and every 6 months in the third year. Only endoscopic examinations were performed in the fourth and fifth years.

Patients who did not achieve cCR, which was confirmed by the triple assessment (DRE, endoscopy, and MRI) with/without histological confirmation, by 24 weeks or who experienced local regrowth during surveillance were referred for salvage surgery if they agreed and were deemed suitable.

Outcome measures

This study assessed oncological outcomes across the entire cohort and two risk groups based on treatment risk stratification: low/intermediate risk (cT1-3ab, N0-1, M0, no EMVI, MRF > 1mm) and high-risk (cT3cd-4/N2, M0, MRF ≤ 1mm and/or EMVI positive). cN2 cases were excluded from the intermediate-risk group due to unspecified extra-nodal or intra-nodal details in MRI reports. Primary endpoints included cCR, rates of local, nodal, regional, and distant relapses, organ preservation rate, disease-free survival (DFS), and overall survival (OS). Local regrowth was defined as luminal recurrence at the site of the original tumour, while nodal relapse referred to recurrence limited to the mesorectal or pelvic lymph nodes. Regional relapse was defined as recurrence in a nearby structure outside the rectum, such as the vaginal wall or presacral space. The organ preservation rate was defined as the absence of transabdominal resection, and the absence of locoregional regrowth unless salvaged by transanal R0 (microscopically clear margin) excisions. DFS was calculated from the last treatment to locoregional recurrence post-R0/R1 (microscopically positive margin) resection, non-salvageable local regrowth/R2 (macroscopically positive margin) resection

post-salvage surgery, the occurrence of second primary/distant metastasis, or last follow-up. OS was measured from the first date of diagnosis to the last date of data review or death from any cause. Secondary outcomes included evaluating the radiation toxicities using Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events (CTCAE) criteria version 5.0 [33] and the influence of patient, tumour, and treatment factors on local tumour control, distant relapse, and survivals.

Statistical analysis

Quantitative data are presented as medians with interquartile range (IQR) or means with standard deviation (SD), while categorical data are presented as counts and percentages. Categorical variables were compared using the χ^2 test, with Fisher's exact test (two-tailed) applied when necessary. Continuous variables were compared using the Mann-Whitney U test due to non-normal distribution. Group survival differences were examined using Kaplan-Meier curves and Log-rank tests were used for statistical assessment. Associations between patient, tumour, and treatment characteristics and survival risks were analysed utilising Cox proportional hazard models. Logistic regression was employed to evaluate binary margin outcomes. Variables with $p \leq 0.2$ in the univariable analyses were included in the multivariable analyses. A p -value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All statistical analyses were conducted using R version 4.4.0.

Results

A total of 402 consecutive patients who had been treated with (chemo)radiation followed by CXB boost therapy were initially identified from the institutional database (2008-2019). After excluding patients with unknown staging (Tx/Nx) ($n=3$), those staged solely by CT scan ($n=16$) (because of its lower sensitivity and specificity for tumour staging compared with MRI [34]), individuals treated palliatively ($n=17$), cases with prior local excision ($n=1$), under-dosed CXB recipients for various reasons (30-60Gy) ($n=18$), and those lost to follow-up ($n=19$), 328 patients were eligible for analysis. The study profile is outlined in *Figure 1*.

With a median follow-up of 33 months and a median age of 73 years, 41% of patients had poor performance status (PS 2-3), and 49% were at high risk for surgery due to age and/or comorbidities. Pre-treatment MRI reports documented MRF involvement in 69%, EMVI in 20%, and tumour gross morphology in nearly 60% of cases. Concurrent chemoradiation was administered to 65.5%, while 20% of high-risk patients received radiotherapy alone as they were not fit for chemotherapy. Restaging MRI was performed in 61% of cases. The mean tumour size decreased from 4.0 ± 1.3 cm to 1.7 ± 0.9 cm post-neoadjuvant treatment. Approximately 69% of patients received a total CXB dose of 90Gy. The treatment gap was ≤ 24 weeks for nearly 88%, with total treatment time for CXB ranging from 4-6 weeks for 66% of patients. Almost 43% of patients had a prolonged overall treatment time [>12 weeks (1 week of EBRT+ 4 weeks of maximal gap time + 4-6 weeks of CXB treatment) for those who had short-course radiotherapy and >25 weeks (5 weeks of EBRT+ 14 weeks of maximal gap time + 4-6 weeks of CXB treatment) for individuals who had long-course (chemo)radiation]. Detailed clinicopathological characteristics for the entire cohort and subgroups are provided in *Table 1*.

This study reported an overall cCR rate of 76.5%, local regrowth rate of 18.3%, nodal relapse rate of 3%, and regional relapse rate of 1.8% (3 patients experienced regional recurrence post-salvage surgery, with 3 cases having concurrent local/nodal relapse). The distant relapse rate was 14%, with approximately 33% of these distant relapses occurring after salvage surgery for residual/regrowth cases, and another 33% experienced isolated relapses after achieving local tumour control. The 3-year and 5-year organ preservation rates were 81% (95% CI: 77-90) and 77% (95% CI: 75-87). DFS rates were 72% (95% CI: 68-77) and 63% (95% CI: 58-72) at three and five years, while OS rates were 80% (95% CI: 75-84) and 65% (95% CI: 63-72) over the same periods. Comprehensive clinical outcomes for each risk group are illustrated with a flow diagram (*Figure 2*).

The initial cCR (78% vs 73%, $p=0.32$), local tumour regrowth (16.6% vs 22.4%, $p=0.41$), nodal relapse (1.8% vs 5.8%, $p=0.051$), and regional relapse (1.3% vs 3.9%, $p=0.33$) rates did not differ significantly between the low/intermediate risk and the high-risk groups. The 3-year cumulative incidence of

local regrowth rates were 18% (95%CI:13-26) and 28% (95%CI:17-38). (*Figure 3A*) However, the high-risk patients experienced a higher risk of distant relapse compared to the low/intermediate-risk group (21.2% vs 10.7%, $p=0.01$) with a 3-year cumulative incidence of distant relapse rates of 21% (95%CI:13-29) vs 14% (95%CI:8-19). (*Figure 3B*) Oncological outcomes with absolute numbers are described in *Table 2*.

The 3-year and 5-year organ preservation rates between the low/intermediate and the high-risk groups were 87% (95% CI: 77-93) vs 80% (95% CI: 71-90) and 85% (95% CI: 77-82) vs 77% (95% CI: 69-90), with the Cox proportional hazard ratio of 1.49 [95% CI: 0.76, 2.92], ($p=0.25$) (*Figure 4A*). The 3-year and 5-year DFS rates were 72% (95% CI: 63-77) vs 64% (95% CI: 61-78) and 70% (95% CI: 56-73) vs 62% (95% CI: 51-75). The Cox proportional hazard ratio was 1.17 [95% CI: 0.77, 1.78], ($p=0.46$) (*Figure 4B*). The OS rates at 3 years and 5 years were 79% (95% CI: 75-85) vs 80% (95% CI: 74-87) and 64% (95% CI: 59-73) vs 67% (95% CI: 60-78), with the Cox proportional hazard ratio of 0.98 [95% CI: 0.70, 1.36], ($p=0.88$) respectively. (*Figure 4C*) No significant difference was observed in terms of organ preservation rate, DFS and OS between groups.

Even in cases where organ preservation failed, subsequent salvage surgeries were feasible for a significant proportion of patients: 39% of low/intermediate risk and 54% of high-risk patients who had residual disease, and 59% and 65% of these respective groups who developed local tumour regrowth. Among them, only two patients experienced R2 resections (*Table 2*). However, information about further postoperative adjuvant chemotherapy for patients with high-risk histological features was not available.

The predominant toxicity following all treatments was late rectal bleeding, primarily presenting as Grade 1-2 occasional self-limiting spotting (17.7%). Grade 3 rectal bleeding, which required blood transfusion, occurred in only three patients (0.9%). Most late rectal bleeding symptoms resolved 2-3 years after CXB treatment. Other symptoms included Grade 1-2 acute proctitis (8.5%), characterised by rectal pain, erratic bowel movements, and/or mucous discharge. Symptoms suggestive of faecal

incontinence (Grade 1-2) (1.2%) and stricture (Grade 1-2) (0.9%) were also reported; these were likely attributed to the (chemo)radiation therapy. The incidence of post-radiation side effects did not significantly differ among the groups ($p=0.16$). (*Table 2*)

Tumour factors such as advanced T-stage, pre- and post-neoadjuvant therapy tumour size (>3 cm), extensive luminal circumferential involvement, and tumour immobility during CXB treatment, along with treatment factors such as neoadjuvant radiation without concurrent chemotherapy, administration of a higher than standard CXB dose >90Gy, and treatment gap >24 weeks were adverse predicting factors for local tumour control. Advanced T-stage and mesorectal fascia involvement were associated with increased distant relapse. Factors including advanced age, high risk for surgery, poor performance status, post-neoadjuvant advanced T-stage (γ T) and tumour size (>3 cm), and external radiotherapy alone were significant indicators for lower DFS and OS. Mesorectal fascia involvement, prolonged overall treatment time, and CXB dose >90Gy were associated with reduced disease-free survival, while exophytic tumours were more likely to demonstrate decreased OS. (*Supplementary tables 1 and 2*)

We have also analysed the patients who received CXB doses that were less than the standard dose of 90Gy and who were excluded from the main study ($n=18$). In this sub-analysis, 15 patients received a CXB dose of 60Gy, while 3 received only 30Gy. The median follow-up period was 40 months (IQR: 12-69), and the median age was 66.5 years (IQR: 58-80). Thirteen patients were classified as low/intermediate risk, and five as high risk. Detailed demographic characteristics for the whole group and subgroups are presented in *Supplementary table 3*.

In the low/intermediate-risk group, the initial cCR rate was 77% (10 out of 13 patients), compared to 60% (3 out of 5 patients) in the high-risk group. No patients in either group experienced local regrowth, nodal, regional, or distant relapses during the follow-up period. In the low/intermediate-risk group, one patient opted to undergo surgery (abdominoperineal resection) after the first CXB fraction, while two patients who had residual disease underwent successful salvage surgeries (low

anterior resections) with R0 margins. In the high-risk group, one patient with residual disease had a salvage abdominoperineal resection (R0), while another was deemed unsuitable for surgery due to advanced age and comorbidities and received optimal supportive care (*Supplementary table 4*). The disease-free survival (DFS) rate for the entire cohort was 94% (95% CI: 78-97) at both three and five years, and the overall survival (OS) rate was 78% (95% CI: 65-84) over the same period.

Discussion

In this study, high-risk rectal cancer patients treated with CXB boost following (chemo)radiation showed higher distant relapse rates than low/intermediate-risk patients. Known predictive factors such as more advanced T and N-stages, increased radial involvement, tumour immobility, and lymphovascular invasion [35], lack of administration of (neo)adjuvant chemotherapy before or after (chemo)radiation in some patients [36, 37], and missing data on postoperative adjuvant chemotherapy, which reduces locoregional and distant metastases after salvage surgery in high-risk patients [38], are likely to have contributed to this outcome. A marginally higher risk of nodal relapse (not statistically significant, $p=0.051$) was also observed in the high-risk group, likely due to the higher incidence of nodal metastases (ypN+) with more advanced ypT stage [39] and the challenges in accurately predicting the presence of lymph node metastasis by restaging MRI after (chemo)radiation [40]. However, initial cCR, local regrowth, nodal and regional relapse rates, organ preservation, DFS and OS were not significantly different between groups, possibly due to successful salvage surgeries being performed in over half the patients when organ-preserving treatment failed. Compared to the OPRA study [16], our high-risk group had lower rates of local tumour regrowth (22.4% vs 36%), better 5-year organ preservation (77% vs 54%), and similar DFS (62% vs 64%). We also observed comparable distant failure risk (21.2% vs 20.7-30.4%) and 5-year DFS (62% vs 65-73%) compared to the PRODIGE-23 and RAPIDO trials, while still achieving organ preservation in our high-risk patients [6, 36]. OS rates are difficult to compare due to the older and comorbid populations in our cohort.

The standard management for low-risk rectal cancer patients generally involves radical surgery, while intermediate-risk patients usually start with neoadjuvant therapy before surgery; however, organ-preserving strategies initially administer neoadjuvant therapy for all risk groups. Therefore, we analysed the combined low- and intermediate-risk groups in line with previous studies [31, 41].

Patients in our low/intermediate risk group showed similar rates of 3-year organ preservation (87% vs 68-97%), local tumour regrowth (16.6% vs 15%), and distant relapse (10.7% vs 10%) to those reported in the recently published OPERA trial [31]. Compared to other studies that have used chemoradiation or combined it with high-dose-rate brachytherapy [41-43], our cohort had lower local regrowth (16.6% vs 20-31%) and distant relapse (10.7% vs 9-25.7%) rates with a similar 5-year DFS (70% vs 68%). Additionally, the final organ preservation rate (80% vs 60-70%) was higher than the CARTS [44] and STAR-TREC [45] studies, despite a higher local regrowth rate (16.7% vs 7.7%). A comprehensive comparison of the oncological outcomes of the risk groups in our study with published results using different strategies is demonstrated in *supplementary table 5*.

Post-treatment radiation toxicities, mainly occasional rectal bleeding (G1/2), were comparable between low/intermediate and high-risk groups and similar to those reported in other studies [23, 31]. Only 1.2% of patients experienced faecal incontinence, a common side effect of post-transanal local excisions and high-dose (chemo)radiation affecting anal sphincter function [46, 47]. Most patients reported that rectal bleeding spontaneously resolved 2-3 years after CXB treatment. However, data on long-term complications from other radiation-related toxicities, as well as patient-reported health-related quality of life, were unavailable due to the retrospective observational nature of the study.

Most prognostic factors for local and distant control, DFS and OS in this study were consistent with other published data [35, 48]. Notably, newly identified prognostic indicators were a treatment gap of >24 weeks between therapies, longer overall treatment time, and a CXB dose >90Gy, which impacted local tumour control and disease-free survival. However, prolonged total CXB treatment

time (up to 9 weeks) did not impact any outcomes. Approximately 32% of patients received an additional 20Gy dose (a total of 110Gy), due to minimal visible or palpable residual disease following the standard 90Gy dose. This finding might have reflected a poorer clinical response in these patients, leading to an increased risk of local failure and reduced disease-free survival. Our study, based on retrospective observational data over the last 16 years, has several limitations. These include missing data on tumour biochemistry, molecular assays, and MRI staging reports, which may bias treatment risk stratification. Additionally, evolving radiotherapy techniques which have improved over recent years (from 3D-CRT to IMRT), varying use of concurrent chemotherapy along with radiotherapy in some patients, lack of routine administration of (neo)adjuvant chemotherapy before/after (chemo)radiation in most high-risk cases, prolonged treatment gaps (>12 weeks in half of patients), and missing information about post-operative adjuvant chemotherapy after salvage surgery in patients with high-risk histology could have influenced outcomes. The absence of restaging MRI scans in 33% of cases and technological advancements in MRI during the study period may have also impacted accurate tumour and nodal restaging thereby biasing the suitability of treating with CXB boost therapy as curative intent.

Conclusions

Despite a higher risk of distant relapse, high-risk locally advanced rectal cancer patients had similar initial cCR, local regrowth, nodal and regional relapse rates, organ preservation, DFS and OS compared to low/intermediate risk patients. In addition, this group showed lower local and distant relapse rates and better organ preservation than other organ-preserving strategies, with comparable DFS to all treatments, including radical surgery. Therefore, CXB boost therapy after (chemo)radiation can be considered a viable alternative to radical surgery for high-risk rectal cancers, especially for patients who have life-limiting comorbidities or those who prefer to avoid colostomy. Timely reassessment and prompt referral of patients who have not achieved cCR post-neoadjuvant treatment, as well as optimising CXB dose, are crucial for improving local tumour control and DFS.

Ethics board approval

As this study was a retrospective observational study, it was approved by the institutional audit committee on 3rd May 2022, and no ethical approval was required.

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List of figures

Figure 1: Study profile

cCR: clinical Complete Response, **APER:** Abdomino Peritoneal Excision of Rectum, **Hartmann's:** Hartmann's operation, **LAR:** Low Anterior Resection, **Exenteration:** Pelvic Exenteration, **EMR:** Endoscopic Mucosal Resection, **TEMS:** Transanal Endoscopic Microsurgery, **SBRT:** Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy, **BSC:** Best Supportive Care

Figure 2: Flow diagram illustrating the oncological outcomes of the two risk groups

	0	12	24	36	48	60
At Risk	175	136	104	81	53	29
Events	0	14	25	29	30	30
1						
At Risk	76	62	42	33	25	12
Events	0	6	16	18	20	20

Figure 3: Cumulative incidence of local regrowth (A) and distant relapse (B) among risk groups

Figure 4: Kaplan-Meier curves for organ preservation rate (A), disease-free survival (B), and overall survival in the two risk groups

Supplementary figure 1: Example of treatment response in high-risk rectal cancer

Table 1: Clinicopathological characteristics of the whole cohort and sub-groups

Characteristics		Total n=328(%)	Treatment risk stratification		
			Low -intermediate n=224(%)	High n=104(%)	P value
Median follow-up (IQR) (months)		33(15-54)	36(12-53)	39(16-57)	0.15 [‡]
Age (years)	Median (IQR)	73(62-80)	72(63-81)	70(60-79)	0.77 [‡]
Gender	Female	89(27)	56(25)	33(32)	0.20 [¥]
	Male	239(73)	168(75)	71(68)	
WHO performance status	0-1	192(59)	124(55)	68(65)	0.09 [¥]
	2-3	136(41)	100(45)	36(35)	
Fitness for surgery	Fit	168(51)	107(48)	61(59)	0.07 [¥]
	High risk	160(49)	117(52)	43(41)	
cT stage	T1	1(0.3)	1(0.4)	0(0)	<0.001 [¥]
	T2	117(35.7)	112(50)	5(4.8)	
	T3 (unspecified)	69(21)	39(17.4)	30(28.8)	
	T3a	74(22.6)	57(25.4)	17(16.3)	
	T3b	40(12.2)	15(6.7)	25(24)	
	T3c	5(1.5)	0(0)	5(4.8)	
	T4 (unspecified)	1(0.3)	0(0)	1(1)	
	T4a	16(4.9)	0(0)	16(15.4)	
	T4b	5(1.5)	0(0)	5(4.8)	
cN stage	N0	172(53)	144(64)	28(27)	<0.001 [¥]
	N1	103(31)	80(36)	23(22)	
	N2	53(16)	0(0)	53(51)	
TNM stage	Stage I	84(25.6)	83(37)	1(1)	<0.001 [¥]
	Stage IIA	74(22.6)	60(26.8)	14(13)	
	Stage IIB	7(2)	0(0)	7(7)	
	Stage IIC	5(1.5)	0(0)	5(5)	
	Stage IIIA	32(9.8)	30(13.4)	2(2)	
	Stage IIIB	73(22.3)	51(22.8)	22(21)	
	Stage IIIC	53(16.2)	0(0)	53(51)	
Mesorectal fascia involvement	Positive	63(19)	0(0)	63(61)	<0.001 [¥]
	Negative	164(50)	146(65)	18(17)	
	Not recorded	101(31)	78(35)	23(22)	
Extramural venous invasion	Positive	36(11)	0(0)	36(34)	<0.001 [¥]
	Negative	31(9)	25(11)	6(6)	
	Not recorded	261(80)	199(89)	62(60)	
Histological differentiation	Well/Moderate	203(62)	134(60)	69(66)	0.57 [¥]
	Poor/Mucinous	10(3)	7(3)	3(3)	
	Not recorded	115(35)	83(37)	32(31)	
Tumour gross morphology	Exophytic	109(33.2)	83(37)	26(25)	<0.001 [¥]
	Flat	15(4.6)	13(6)	2(1)	
	Ulcerated/Combined	71(21.6)	34(15)	37(36)	
	Not recorded	133(40.6)	94(42)	39(38)	
Tumour circumferential involvement	<half	214(65)	158 (71)	56(54)	<0.001 [¥]
	≥half	68(21)	33(15)	35(34)	
	Not recorded	46(14)	33(14)	13(12)	
Tumour mobility at time of CXB	Mobile	151(46)	110(49)	41(39)	0.90 [¥]
	Tethered/Indurated	39(12)	28(13)	11(11)	
	Not recorded	138(42)	86(38)	52(50)	
Mean initial tumour size (cm)		4.0±1.3	3.7±1.2	4.5±1.4	<0.001 [‡]
Initial tumour size group	≤3cm	106(32)	87(39)	19(18)	<0.001 [¥]
	>3-10cm	212(65)	129(57)	83(80)	
	Not recorded	10(3)	8(4)	2(2)	

Mean tumour size at time of CXB (cm)		1.7±0.9	1.6±0.9	1.8±1.1	0.19 [‡]
Tumour size group at CXB	≤3cm	315(96)	218(97)	97(93)	0.16 [¥]
	>3-5cm	12(3.7)	6(3)	6(6)	
	Not recorded	1(0.3)	0(0)	1(1)	
Distance from anal verge	3-≤6cm	226(69)	152(68)	74(71)	0.72 [¥]
	>6-12cm	85(26)	59(26)	26(25)	
	Not recorded	17(5)	13(6)	4(4)	
EBRT regimen	Short course	54(16.5)	48(21.4)	6(5.8)	<0.001 [¥]
	Long course	59(18.0)	44(19.6)	15(14.4)	
	Chemoradiation	215(65.5)	132(59)	83(79.8)	
Restaging with MRI	Yes	201(61)	85(38)	78(75)	0.001 [¥]
	No	107(33)	123(55)	22(21)	
	Not recorded	20(6)	16(7)	4(4)	
Stage after (chemo)radiation	γT0,γN0,γM0	41(12.5)	20(9)	21(20)	0.02 [¥]
	γT1/2,γN0,γM0	120(36.5)	84(37)	36(35)	
	γT2/3,γN0,γM0	34(10)	17(8)	17(16)	
	γT3/4,γN0,γM0	6(2)	2(1)	4(4)	
	Unknown	127 (39)	101(45)	26(25)	
Treatment gap time between EBRT and CXB	<12 weeks	155(47.3)	115(51.3)	40(39)	0.07 [¥]
	12-24 weeks	132(40.2)	85(38)	47(45)	
	>24-48 weeks	41(12.5)	24(10.7)	17(16)	
Overall treatment time	Conventional	188(57.3)	130(58)	58(55.8)	0.70 [¥]
	Unconventional	140(42.7)	94(42)	46(44.2)	
CXB total dose	80-90Gy	224(68.3)	152(68)	72(69)	0.80 [¥]
	110Gy	104(31.7)	72(32)	32(31)	
Total CXB treatment time	Standard (4-6 weeks)	216(66)	149(66.5)	67(64)	0.71 [¥]
	Unconventional (>6-9 weeks)	112(34)	75(33.5)	37(36)	

IQR: Interquartile Range, WHO: World Health Organization, EBRT: External Beam Radiation, CXB: Contact X-ray Brachytherapy, MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging, †= Mann-Whitney U test, ¥= χ^2 test

Table 2: Oncological and clinical outcomes of the whole cohort and risk group studies

Outcome	Total n=328(%)	Risk stratification		P value (χ^2 test)
		Low/intermediate n=224(%)	High n=104(%)	
Near/complete Clinical Response (n/cCR)	251(76.5)	175(78)	76(73)	0.32
Residual disease	77(23.5)	49(22)	28(27)	
Number of patients who underwent salvage surgery and outcomes	34/77 (44) R0=27 R1=6 R2=1	19/49(39) R0=18 R1=1	15/28 (54) R0=9 R1=5 R2=1	
Local regrowth	46/251(18.3)	29/175(16.6)	17/76(22.4)	0.41
Number of patients who underwent salvage surgery and outcomes	28/46 (61) R0=22 R1=5 R2=1	17/29 (59) R0=14 R1=3	11/17 (65) R0=8 R1=2 R2=1	
Nodal relapse	10(3.0)	4(1.8)	6(5.8)	0.051
Regional relapse	6(1.8)	3(1.3)	3(2.9)	0.33
Number of patients (both nodal and regional) who underwent salvage surgery and outcomes	7/16 (44) R0=4 R1=2 CR=1	5/7 (71) R0=2 R1=2 (SBRT – CR)	2/9 (22) R0=2	
Distant relapse	46(14)	24(10.7)	22(21.2)	0.01
Number of patients who underwent salvage surgery and outcomes	6/46 (13) All CR	2/24 (8) Lung resection=2	4/22 (18) Lung resection=3 Liver resection=1	
Total incidence of radiation toxicities	96(29.3)	64(28.6)	32(30.8)	0.16
Acute proctitis (erratic bowel, pain)				
Grade 1-2	28(8.5)	20(9)	8(7.7)	
Grade 3	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	
Late rectal bleeding				
Grade 1/2	58(17.7)	35(15.6)3(1.4)	23(22.3)	
Grade 3	3(0.9)		0(0)	
Faecal incontinence				
Grade 1-2	4(1.2)	3(1)	1(0.9)	
Grade 3	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	
Stricture				
Grade 1-2	3(0.9)	3(3.7)	0(0)	
Grade 3	0(0)	0(0)	0(0)	

R0= microscopically negative margin resection, R1= microscopically positive margin resection, R2= macroscopically positive margin resection, SBRT= Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy, CR= Complete Response

Supplementary Table on Generalizability of Study Population(s)

Condition	Description
Disease, problem, or condition under investigation	High-risk locally advanced rectal adenocarcinoma
Relevant considerations of disease, problem, or condition in relation to:	<i>Note any relevant considerations in boxes below:</i>
Sex and gender	In 2019, 142,462 cases of colon and rectum cancer were reported in the UK: 75,581 among males and 66,881 among females. The incidence rate was 36 per 100,000 standard population and was 42 per 100,000 males and 32 per 100,000 females.
Age	Incidence rates for bowel cancer in the UK are highest in people aged 85 to 89 (2017-2019). Each year more than 4 in 10 (43%) of all new bowel cancer cases in the UK are diagnosed in people aged 75 and over (2017-2019).
Race or ethnic group	Incidence rates for bowel cancer are lower in the Asian and Black ethnic groups, and in people of mixed or multiple ethnicity, compared with the White ethnic group, in England (2013-2017).
Geography	Large geographical variations in incidence and mortality rates are observed. The incidence rates are highest in Europe and Australia and New Zealand, and the mortality rates are highest in Eastern Europe.
Other considerations	
Study	Description
Overall assessment of generalizability of the study population	This study was conducted in an older cohort with a median age of 73(IQR:62-80) years, who had high-risk locally advanced rectal cancer. 73% of patients were male. Data on ethnicity was not available, although the majority were white British. All patients were from the United Kingdom. The treatment protocol used in this study is applicable to all populations.